

A Novel Indoor Localization Scheme for Autonomous Nodes in IEEE 802.15.4a Networks

G. Rébel^{*†}, J. González[†], P. Glösekötter,^{*} Francisco Estevez^{*} and Adrian Romero^{*}

^{*} Lab. for Semiconductor Devices & Bussystems

University of Applied Sciences of Münster, Münster, Germany

Email: gregor@fh-muenster.de, gloesek@ieee.org, fjestevz@ieee.org, ar461827@fh-muenster.de

[†] Dept. of Computer Architecture and Technology

University of Granada, Granada, Spain

Email: gregorrebel@correo.ugr.es, jesusgonzalez@ugr.es

Abstract—Ultra Wide Band (UWB) transceivers that are compliant to IEEE 802.15.4a standard do not provide distance measurement on their own. Instead they incorporate a high frequency counter (e.g. 64 Ghz) and a precise timestamp mechanism for outgoing and incoming data frames. The distance measurement has to be implemented by an external software.

Different localization schemes exist but these are optimized to provide the position information in the fixed anchor nodes first. The anchor nodes then have to use additional transmissions to send the information to the mobile node.

The term autonomous (mobile) node should mean that the position data is required by each mobile node itself. The new proposed localization algorithm accumulates the required localization information in the mobile node first by using less transmissions (and therefore less time and energy) than existing algorithms.

Index Terms—IEEE 802.15.4a, Ultra Wide Band, Localization, Indoor, Algorithm

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Indoor Localization using Ultra Wide Band Radios

The localization of a mobile node in 3D space requires to take ranging measures to four other nodes which positions are already known. The amount of required ranging measures can be reduced if some coordinates are fixed (e.g. the node is always located on a flat surface) or can be calculated (e.g. the node is located on a surface which height map is known). The algorithm used to locate a node is not part of this paper. Instead the focus is on the key technique of range measurement to one or more fixed anchor nodes.

B. Metric of Energy Consumption

IEEE 802.15.4a UWB transceivers require more energy to transmit or receive data frames than previous technologies. The power draw of an UWB transceiver is typically the same, if not higher, while its receiver is switched on as during transmitting. In order to minimize the energy consumption per localization, the sum of all time periods when the transmitter or receiver is enabled has to be minimized.

II. STATE OF ART

A. Time Difference Of Arrival (TDOA)

This ranging algorithm uses one mobile node M and two or more fixed anchor Nodes A_1, \dots, A_n as shown in fig. 1. The

Fig. 1: Localization via Time Differential of Arrival (TDOA)

Fig. 2: Ranging via Time Of Flight Single Sided (TOF-SS)

mobile node M sends out a message that is received and timestamped by A_1, \dots, A_n . The anchor nodes then communicate with each other to locate M based on the different arrival timestamps $TS - i, i = [1, \dots, n]$. This algorithm only requires one message to be transmitted by the mobile node. The big disadvantage of this method is that the anchor nodes must precisely synchronize their clocks. This synchronization can be difficult (e.g. if the anchor nodes cannot communicate with each other directly). TDOA is not part of this paper and is only presented for completeness.

B. Time Of Flight Ranging Single Sided (TOF-SS)

TOF ranging measures the distance between two nodes. In the context of localization these typically are a mobile node M and a fixed anchor node A_i . The single sided version is the

(1)	$T_{ReplyA_i} = TS_{A_i,TX_1} - TS_{A_i,RX_1}$
(2)	$T_{RoundM_i} = TS_{M,RX_1} - TS_{M,TX_1} - T_{ReplyA_i}$
(3)	$T_{ReplyM} = TS_{M,TX_1} - TS_{M,RX_1}$
(4)	$T_{RoundA_i} = TS_{A_i,RX_2} - TS_{A_i,TX_1} - T_{ReplyM}$

TABLE I: Formulas - Time Of Flight Ranging

most simple TOF implementation. For this, Node M has to transmit one request- and to receive one reply-message named $M_{Request_i}$ and M_{ReplyA_i} in fig. 2. Node M takes timestamps TS_{M,TX_1} and TS_{M,RX_1} when transmitting $M_{Request_i}$ and receiving M_{ReplyA_i} . Node B will transmit a ranging reply message M_{ReplyA_i} after a fixed delay time T_{ReplyA_i} . The physical distance between M and A_i is then proportional to the round trip time T_{RoundM_i} , as calculated in table I. T_{ReplyA_i} should be as short as possible but may vary among individual nodes. T_{ReplyA_i} must be long enough to allow Node A_i to read and process the received ranging request and to prepare the answer message. The required minimum delay time depends on the actual processing speed of the used microcontroller and its firmware. T_{ReplyA_i} may vary between different radio nodes with same hardware. As node M requires the exact delay time to calculate the distance, T_{ReplyA_i} is sent with M_{ReplyA_i} . Different transceivers always differ in their clock speed. T_{ReplyA_i} is measured by using the clock of node A_i while T_{RoundM_i} is measured by using the clock of node M. The effect of clock induced error in single sided TOF ranging also depends on T_{ReplyA_i} and the frame length. E.g. for the DecaWave DW1000 transceiver, varying $T_{ReplyA_i} = 0.1 \dots 5$ ms and ClockError = 2 ... 40 parts per million (ppm) will affect the measurement of T_{ReplyA_i} from 0.1 ns to 100ns. Where 1 ns corresponds to a 30 cm error in measured distance [1].

C. Time Of Flight Ranging Double Sided (TOF-DS)

Clock induced errors can be reduced by using double sided TOF ranging as shown in fig. 3. This basically requires one additional transmission from node M to A_i using an exact reply time T_{ReplyM} . T_{ReplyM} is required to calculate a second round trip time T_{RoundA_i} as shown in table I. As T_{ReplyM} is measured using the clock of node M, the different clock speeds of M and A_i will compensate each other. Even a relative clock error of 40 ppm will induce an error in distance measure of less than 2.2 mm for a practical setup [1]. Double Sided TOF ranging is implemented as software libraries for various commercially available IEEE 801.15.4a transceivers like DecaWave DW1000 [1] and Nanotron nanoLOC [2].

D. TOF Ranging Symmetric Double Sided (TOF-SDS)

Double Sided TOF ranging with equal reply times in both participating nodes is called Symmetric Double Sided TOF (SDS TOF). SDS TOF minimizes the clock induced error as crystal frequency variations are halved [3]. For asymmetric double sided TOF ranging [4] has shown a method to minimize the clock induced error to a value similar to SDS TOF ranging.

Fig. 3: Ranging via Time Of Flight Double Sided (TOF-DS and TOF-SDS)

Fig. 4: Ranging TOF-TRADS with Forward Reporting

E. TOF Ranging Traffic Reduced Asymmetric Double Sided (TOF-TRADS)

Mi-Kyung Oh et al [5] presented a ranging scheme that reduces clock induced error without increasing the amount of transmitted messages. The basic idea is to measure the same response delay on two nodes. The two time measures are then used to calculate the relative frequency offset. Two basic variants exist which each require three messages to be exchanged. Similar ranging schemes, that also measure the same time period on different nodes, have later been proposed by Hakyong Kim [6] and by Myungkyun Kwak and Jongwha Chong [7].

The basic TOF-TRADS scheme works as follows: Node M sends a Request to Node A_i . Node A_i sends a reply message

Fig. 5: Ranging TOF-TRADS with Backward Reporting

Fig. 6: Localization with Traffic Reduced Asymmetric Double Sided Time Of Flight Ranging (TOF-TRADS)

back to Node M after a fixed delay T_{ReplyA_i1} . With forward reporting (fig. 4), node M sends a reply message after a fixed delay time after receiving the reply message from A_i . Node A_i measures time period $T_{ReplyA_i2} = TS_{A_i,RX2} - TS_{A_i,TX1} - T_{RoundM_i}$. The CFO_{Ratio} can then be calculated the same way as in backward reporting scheme. With backward reporting (fig. 5), node A_i then sends a second reply message after a fixed delay. Node M knows the timestamps $TS_{M,RX1}$ and $TS_{M,RX2}$ of both reply messages. T_{ReplyM_i} is simply the difference between both timestamps. The clock frequency offset ratio $CFO_{Ratio} = T_{ReplyM_i} / T_{ReplyA_i2}$ is the relative clock frequency offset of both radios. This ratio allows to compensate the clock induced error.

F. Localization using TOF-TRADS

Mi-Kyung Oh et al [5] describe how to use their traffic reduced asymmetric double sided time of flight ranging for indoor localization. The basic localization scheme is shown in fig. 6. Multiple anchor nodes $A_i, i = [1, \dots, n]$ each send

Fig. 7: Localization via Double Sided TOF Ranging with Cascaded Replies from n Anchors (TOF-CR)

one localization request $M_{RequestA_1}$ to the same mobile node M. The requests arrive at M at time stamps $TS_{M,RX1}$. Node M sends a first broadcast reply message $M_{ReplyM,1}$ after delay time $T_{M,Delay1}$ after receiving the last ranging request $M_{RequestAn}$. Node M broadcasts a second reply message $M_{ReplyM,2}$ after another delay time $T_{M,Delay2}$. The anchor nodes receive both reply messages and measure their receiving timestamps $TS_{A_i,RX1}$ and $TS_{A_i,RX2}$. The difference between both timestamps represents the same delay time but it is measured with the local clock and used to calculate CFO_{Ratio} as described above. The delay times are embodied in $M_{ReplyM,1}$ and $M_{ReplyM,2}$ respectively. Each anchor node is then able to calculate the round trip time T_{RoundA_i} and compensate the CFO. The transmit times $TS_{A_i,TX1}$ must be timed exactly among all anchor and mobile nodes to minimize the total receiver on time of node M while avoiding collisions. At the end of this localization scheme, each anchor node knows its distance to the mobile node.

III. PROPOSED LOCALIZATION SCHEME

The TOF-TRADS scheme requires $n + 2$ messages to calculate the distance from n anchor nodes to a mobile Node M. Using TOF-SDS ranging n times would require $3n$ messages. TOF-TRADS therefore requires less messages than n times TOF-SDS for $n \geq 1$. But TOF-TRADS it has two disadvantages:

- The localization process is initiated by the anchor nodes. This requires that the mobile node switches on its receiver at a predefined time which increases its energy usage.
- At the end of the localization scheme, the gathered range information is distributed over n anchor nodes. This information has to be sent to the mobile node by n additional transmissions.

A. Localization via TOF with Cascaded Replies (TOF-CR)

A novel localization scheme called TOF Ranging with Cascaded Replies (TOF-CR) is intended to overcome these

disadvantages as shown in fig. 7. In TOF-CR, a mobile node broadcasts a ranging request message MRrequest to n anchor nodes $A_i, i = [1, \dots, n]$. Each anchor node answers after a unique reply time T_{ReplyA_i} . The reply messages are received by node M at timestamps T_{SM,RX_i} . From these, round trip times T_{RoundM_i} are calculated analogue to table I. Node M then sends all calculated round trip times plus its own reply time T_{ReplyM} in one reply message M_{ReplyM} . This final reply message is sent after a known delay T_{DelayM} after T_{SM,TX_i} via broadcast to all anchor nodes. The delay time is also measured in each anchor node as T_{DelayA_i} . As for TOF-TRADS, these multiple measures of the same time period allow to compensate CFO.

B. Predicting Relative CFO in Periodic Localization (TOF-CRP)

When multiple localizations take place in a short time, then the relative CFO between a mobile node and the available anchor nodes is expected to be stable. This stationary state allows to cache relative CFOs for each anchor in the mobile node. The n anchor nodes will not send their calculated relative CFO in the current localization process. Instead, each anchor node A_i will send the relative CFO in its MReplyA.i message at the beginning of the next localization process as shown in fig. 7. This makes it possible to provide a compensated position in the mobile node with only n + 2 messages beginning from the second localization.

C. Localization via TOF with Dynamic Cascaded Replies (TOF-DCRP)

TOF-DCRP shall be an extension to TOF-CRP where a large amount of anchor nodes is deployed in a region or a building. When the amount of anchor nodes is high, then TOF-CR will result in a very long T_{ReplyM} . This means that node M has to switch on its receiver for a long time to receive even the anchor node with longest T_{ReplyA_i} . Node M may switch off its receiver after receiving enough round trip times for a localization. Unfortunately, in a large scale setup, most anchor nodes will be out of reach. If only An-3, ..., An are in reach, then node M has to wait the complete T_{DelayM} to obtain enough ranging data to localize itself. As an optimization, anchor nodes which are far away from each other may reuse the same reply time T_{ReplyA_i} in a dynamic way. It is assumed, that the anchor nodes are located in a sensefull setup. Which means that, for every mobile location, not much more than four anchor nodes are in reach. As UWB-Transceivers are reflected by typical walls, this assumption seems to be realistic inside buildings. Each room may be equipped with four anchor nodes. Adjacent rooms or a floor may add to the group of anchor nodes in reach. But anchor nodes in not adjacent rooms should ideally be out of reach. Different dynamic scheduling schemes for UWB ranging are described in [8] and a joint scheduling algorithm based on integer linear program (ILP) is described in [9] and may be investigated during this research line.

Scheme	1st Data	Initiator	Example Application Scenario
TDOA	Anchors	Mobile	Indoor Asset Tracking
TOF-SDS	Initiator	Anyone	General Purpose
TOF-TRADS	Anchors	Anchor	Indoor Asset Tracking
TOF-CRP	Mobile	Mobile	Autonomous Indoor Navigation
TOF-DCRP	Mobile	Mobile	Autonomous Indoor Navigation

TABLE II: Localization Scheme Comparison

D. Best Localization Scheme for Autonomous Nodes

Individual localization schemes differ in the place where the 3D location of a node is available first during the process of localization. For autonomous mobile nodes, we claim that the 3D location is required in the mobile node first. Localization schemes that gather ranging information in n anchor nodes will require n additional messages to concentrate all required data in the mobile node. The TOF-CRP and TOF-DCRP are initiated by the mobile node and provide the position in the mobile node first. This makes them the best localization schemes for autonomous mobile nodes. Table II categorizes different localization schemes by their typical application scenario. The table shows where all required localization data is available first and which node type initiates the localization.

IV. METHODOLOGY

The communication protocols for TOF-CRP and TOF-DCRP localization schemes will be implemented using the C programming language. The software development bases on an open source operating system and development toolchain for 32 bit microcontrollers called The ToolChain [10]. A new software driver for an IEEE 802.15.4a compliant Ultra Wide Band transceiver from DecaWave Corp called DW1000 has been developed for The ToolChain. The new proposed localization scheme will be implemented on top of this software driver. The localization scheme will be tested on prototype boards equipped with a STM32L100 microcontroller and this DW1000 transceiver. The network simulations for a large amount of distributed anchor nodes will be performed using a software simulator.

V. CONCLUSION

We have presented a novel localization scheme TOF-CR for IEEE 802.15.4a UWB sensor networks that requires less transmissions than state of the art schemes in a special scenario where localization is initiated by each mobile node and the localization data is required in the mobile node first. An extension TOF-CRP has been described that allows CFO compensation without extra transmissions during periodic localizations. Another extension TOF-DCRP has been described for setups with large amount of anchor nodes.

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